

Electrophysiological Biomarkers for Non-clinical Safety Evaluation of Neuro-interventional Devices

Catalog of Regulatory Science Tools to Help Assess New Medical Devices

Technical Description

The objective of this tool is to assist sponsors and the FDA reviewers for a comprehensive analysis of benefit-risk of neuro-interventional devices and describes methods for data acquisition and analysis. Brain electrophysiological signals can be acquired with invasive or non-invasive electrodes. This tool includes several quantitative electrophysiological features that would change after occurrence of brain damage. Detection of such changes implies a safety concern, and the degree of change suggests the level of risk.

Intended Purpose

The tool has been characterized through animal studies in brain injuries induced by ultrasound and mechanical impact and has been compared to other methods used in the non-clinical safety evaluation of neuro-interventional devices. Furthermore, results of this work were further validated by analysis of electrophysiological data from human subjects acquired a brain injury.

The following peer-reviewed research includes the detailed characterization and verification methods and results:

- Ye M, Solarana K, Rafi H, Patel S, Nabili M, Liu Y, Huang S, Fisher JAN, Krauthamer V, Myers M, Welle C. Longitudinal Functional Assessment of Brain Injury Induced by High-Intensity Ultrasound Pulse Sequences. *Sci Rep.* 2019 Oct 29;9(1):15518. PubMed PMID: [31664091](#); PubMed Central PMCID: [PMC6820547](#).
- Huang S, Fisher JAN, Ye M, Kim YS, Ma R, Nabili M, Krauthamer V, Myers MR, Coleman TP, Welle CG. Epidermal Electrode Technology for Detecting Ultrasonic Perturbation of Sensory Brain Activity. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng.* 2018 Jun;65(6):1272-1280. PubMed PMID: [28858781](#). [PMC9472568](#)
- Fisher JA, Huang S, Ye M, Nabili M, Wilent WB, Krauthamer V, Myers MR, Welle CG. Real-Time Detection and Monitoring of Acute Brain Injury Utilizing Evoked Electroencephalographic Potentials. *IEEE Trans Neural Syst Rehabil Eng.* 2016 Sep;24(9):1003-1012. PubMed PMID: [26955039](#). [PMC9479576](#)
- Jang H, Huang S, Hammer DX, Wang L, Rafi H, **Ye M**, Welle CG, Fisher JAN. Alterations in Neurovascular Coupling Following Acute Traumatic Brain Injury. *Neurophotonics.* 2017; 4(4) [PMC5741992](#)

- Vivaldi N, Caiola M, Solarana K, Ye M. Evaluating Performance of EEG Data-Driven Machine Learning for Traumatic Brain Injury Classification. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng.* 2021; 68(11), 3205-3216. PMID: [33635785](#) [PMC9513823](#)

Testing

The software tool is initially tested with successful execution over a synthetic ECG [1] by adding noise segments from the MIT-BIH Noise Stress Test (NST) database [2].

The effects of estimated noise by the software are visually assessed against the clean ECGs from select datasets. In addition, the software is assessed by quantitatively comparing the effects of the noise obtained using this software against the effects of the noise obtained by merely removing the QRS complex from the ECG signals. This assessment was separately performed using the simulated data as described in [1].

Limitations

- To acquire brain electrophysiological signals, certain invasive or noninvasive procedures and equipment are required. Please see the Supporting documents for procedures and equipment.
- Baseline is required to identify the change

Supporting Documentation

Please refer to the Supporting Document for data acquisition and analysis procedures. In addition, more detailed information can be found in the following publications:

These three papers described two minimally invasive methods, namely epidural recording, for the acquisition of the data and two methods of data analysis (median-nerve stimulation induced somatosensory evoked potential and resting state brain waves):

- Ye M, Solarana K, Rafi H, Patel S, Nabili M, Liu Y, Huang S, Fisher JAN, Krauthamer V, Myers M, Welle C. Longitudinal Functional Assessment of Brain Injury Induced by High-Intensity Ultrasound Pulse Sequences. *Sci Rep.* 2019 Oct 29;9(1):15518. PubMed PMID: [31664091](#); PubMed Central PMCID: [PMC6820547](#).
- Fisher JA, Huang S, Ye M, Nabili M, Wilent WB, Krauthamer V, Myers MR, Welle CG. Real-Time Detection and Monitoring of Acute Brain Injury Utilizing Evoked Electroencephalographic Potentials. *IEEE Trans Neural Syst Rehabil Eng.* 2016 Sep;24(9):1003-1012. PubMed PMID: [26955039](#). [PMC9479576](#)
- Jang H, Huang S, Hammer DX, Wang L, Rafi H, Ye M, Welle CG, Fisher JAN. Alterations in Neurovascular Coupling Following Acute Traumatic Brain Injury. *Neurophotonics.* 2017; 4(4) [PMC5741992](#)

This paper described a non-invasive method for the data acquisition.

Huang S, Fisher JAN, Ye M, Kim YS, Ma R, Nabili M, Krauthamer V, Myers MR, Coleman TP, Welle CG.

Epidermal Electrode Technology for Detecting Ultrasonic Perturbation of Sensory Brain Activity. IEEE Trans Biomed Eng. 2018 Jun;65(6):1272-1280. PubMed PMID: [28858781](#). [PMC9472568](#).

Relevant Publications

[1]. Galeotti, L. and C.G. Scully, [A method to extract realistic artifacts from electrocardiogram recordings for robust algorithm testing](#). Journal of Electrocardiology, 2018. **51**(6, Supplement): p. S56-S60.

[2]. Moody GB, M.W., Mark RG, [A noise stress test for arrhythmia detectors.](#), in [Computers in Cardiology](#). 1984. p. 381-384

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Tool Reference

In addition to citing relevant publications please reference the use of this tool using DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8229816

For more information

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